

Study of Functional Status of Spinal Accessory Nerve Following Different Types of Neck Dissection in Head and Neck Cancer

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Abstract:**Background:** Neck dissection is a fundamental treatment for lymph node metastases in head and neck cancer, with varying implications for the spinal accessory nerve (SAN) function, which is crucial for shoulder mobility.**Methods:** This prospective study at Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute involved 100 patients undergoing neck dissection. The study assessed SAN function, shoulder dysfunction, and electromyography (EMG) of the trapezius muscle pre- and post-operatively at 3 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months. Patients were divided into groups undergoing elective neck dissection and observation.**Results:** Initial SAN function was significantly impaired in the elective dissection group but showed improvement over time. Shoulder dysfunction and EMG findings varied with the type of dissection, with radical dissections causing more significant impairments. Physiotherapy significantly improved pain and shoulder mobility.**Conclusion:** Elective neck dissection impacts SAN function and shoulder mobility, with recovery influenced by the extent of dissection and rehabilitative interventions. Tailoring surgical approaches and reinforcing postoperative rehabilitation are vital for optimizing patient outcomes.**Keywords:** Neck dissection, spinal accessory nerve, shoulder dysfunction, head and neck cancer, physiotherapy, electromyography.

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Introduction

Neck dissection (ND) stands as a cornerstone in the management of head and neck cancer, particularly for addressing the critical prognostic factor of lymph node metastasis. While this surgical strategy is pivotal in curtailing disease progression, it harbors the potential for significant morbidity, among which, the impairment of the spinal accessory nerve (SAN) is notably consequential. The SAN, or the eleventh cranial nerve, plays an integral role in shoulder and arm mobility by innervating the trapezius muscle, which is essential for shoulder elevation and arm movement. [1,2]

The functional integrity of the SAN is paramount for maintaining shoulder girdle stability and range of motion. Disruption or injury to this nerve during neck dissection can lead to shoulder dysfunction, characterized by a painful and disabling syndrome that significantly affects a patient's quality of life. This condition, often manifested as shoulder drop and limited arm abduction, results primarily from the resultant atrophy of the trapezius muscle. However, the clinical detection of such nerve impairments can be challenging. Subtle deficits in shoulder function may be overshadowed by

compensatory mechanisms enacted by surrounding muscles, such as the deltoid and the supraspinatus, which can mask the extent of SAN injury. [3,4] Electromyography (EMG) has emerged as a critical diagnostic tool in this context, offering an objective assessment of muscle and nerve function. This non-invasive technique measures the electrical activity produced by muscles, providing valuable insights into the neuromuscular interactions that underlie movements such as arm elevation. Surface EMG, in particular, allows for the evaluation of superficial muscle activity in a manner that is both patient-friendly and clinically informative, making it an indispensable tool in the postoperative assessment of patients who have undergone ND. [5,6]

Despite its utility, the application of EMG in the early postoperative period remains underutilized. Most existing studies have concentrated on long-term outcomes and rehabilitation strategies, often overlooking the immediate post-surgical phase when early intervention could be most beneficial. Recognizing this gap, the current study aims to harness both clinical assessments and

electromyographic data to paint a comprehensive picture of the functional repercussions on the spinal accessory nerve following various types of neck dissections. [7,8] Moreover, this study seeks to explore the role of early physiotherapy in the rehabilitation of patients with SAN injury. While initial findings suggest only marginal benefits from immediate postoperative exercises, there is burgeoning evidence supporting the efficacy of prolonged physiotherapy regimes. Through a detailed examination of 100 patients subjected to ND for head and neck cancers, this research endeavours to elucidate the early and long-term therapeutic impacts of physiotherapy on shoulder dysfunction, thereby contributing to the enhancement of patient care and rehabilitation protocols in this vulnerable population.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting and Duration

This prospective, observational study was conducted at the Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, from December 2011 to February 2014.

Participants

The study cohort comprised 100 patients undergoing neck dissection for head and neck cancers. Patients eligible for inclusion were those admitted to the Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute requiring curative R0 resection neck dissection, aged 18 years and older, and both male and female.

Exclusion criteria included patients unfit for general anesthesia (GA), those with preoperative radiotherapy, bilateral neck dissection requirement, existing neurological or orthopedic conditions affecting the neck and shoulder, prior shoulder pathologies (e.g., fractures, trauma), pre-operative shoulder dysfunction, shoulder myopathy, or unwillingness to participate in the study.

Sampling Technique

Patients were selected using a random sampling technique to ensure unbiased distribution across the study.

Data Collection and Study Design

Upon admission, a comprehensive history and systemic examination were conducted, and necessary investigations were performed for meticulous cancer staging. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. Patients were then randomized into two groups: Group A underwent elective neck dissection, and Group B was observed without surgical intervention. Baseline assessments included range of motion (ROM) measurements using a standard goniometer and EMG to evaluate the trapezius muscle innervation.

EMG was performed preoperatively and postoperatively at specified intervals by a blinded physiotherapy expert using surface electrodes and needle EMG techniques.

Intervention

Neck dissection procedures varied among participants and included radical neck dissection (RND), modified neck dissection (MND), and selective neck dissection (SND), with careful identification and preservation of the spinal accessory nerve during dissection at critical anatomical points.

Follow-Up and Outcome Measures

Patients were followed up postoperatively at the 3rd week, 3rd month, and 6th month. The primary outcomes included changes in shoulder function and nerve integrity assessed through clinical examination and EMG studies. Pain and shoulder function were quantitatively assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) and goniometry.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables such as EMG findings were compared using Student's t-test, while categorical data such as nerve conduction and post-operative complications were analyzed using Fisher's exact test and chi-square tests.

A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All patient data were anonymised and handled according to ethical guidelines to maintain confidentiality and integrity of the research.

Results

The study's results provide valuable insights into the functional outcomes and recovery trajectories of patients undergoing different types of neck dissection for head and neck cancer. With a total of 100 patients evenly divided between elective neck dissection (Group A) and observation (Group B), the demographics showed no significant differences in age or gender distribution across groups, ensuring comparability in the analysis of surgical impacts.

The spinal accessory nerve (SAN) function, critical for shoulder mobility and strength, was closely monitored pre-operatively and at various post-operative stages. Initially, both groups exhibited similar SAN function scores of 95%.

However, post-operative assessments revealed a more significant decline in SAN function in Group A immediately after surgery, which gradually improved over time but remained slightly lower than Group B at the six-month follow-up. This suggests that while elective neck dissection initially

impacts SAN function more severely, recovery is possible with appropriate management.

The incidence of shoulder dysfunction post-surgery, assessed through patient-reported outcomes and objective measurements, was higher in patients undergoing radical neck dissection (RND) with 20% experiencing moderate severity. Modified (MND) and selective (SND) neck dissections resulted in milder and less frequent shoulder dysfunction, highlighting the importance of surgical technique in preserving nerve integrity and function.

Electromyography (EMG) findings provided further granularity to the muscle impact, particularly on the trapezius. A significant

reduction in EMG amplitudes immediately post-surgery was observed across all trapezius parts (upper, middle, and lower), with gradual recovery noted in the follow-up periods. This trajectory indicates the traumatic impact of neck dissection on muscle function, with a progressive return towards baseline function by six months, especially notable in the upper trapezius. Lastly, the effectiveness of physiotherapy was evident in the improvement of both pain scores and range of motion.

Patients showed a marked decrease in pain and enhanced shoulder mobility in flexion and abduction over six months. This underscores the critical role of rehabilitation in enhancing recovery and minimizing long-term disability post-neck dissection.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Variable	Group A (Elective Neck Dissection)	Group B (Observation)
Total Patients	50	50
Age Range (years)	41-60	41-60
Gender Distribution	Male: 76%, Female: 24%	Male: 76%, Female: 24%
Primary Tumor Stage	T1: 46%, T2: 54%	T1: 46%, T2: 54%

Table 2: Pre-Operative and Post-Operative Spinal Accessory Nerve Function

Time point	Mean SAN Function Score (Group A)	Mean SAN Function Score (Group B)
Pre-op	95%	95%
3 Weeks	80%	82%
3 Months	85%	84%
6 Months	90%	85%

Table 3: Incidence of Shoulder Dysfunction Post-Neck Dissection

Type of Neck Dissection	Incidence (%)	Severity (Mild/Moderate/Severe)
RND (Radical)	20%	Moderate
MND (Modified)	15%	Mild
SND (Selective)	10%	Mild

Table 4: EMG Findings of Trapezius Muscle Pre and Post-Neck Dissection

Time point	EMG Amplitude (µV) - Upper Trapezius	EMG Amplitude (µV) - Middle Trapezius	EMG Amplitude (µV) - Lower Trapezius
Pre-op	450 µV	500 µV	550 µV
3 Weeks Post-op	300 µV	350 µV	400 µV
3 Months Post-op	400 µV	450 µV	500 µV
6 Months Post-op	430 µV	480 µV	530 µV

Table 5: Comparison of Physiotherapy Outcomes

Assessment Point	VAS for Pain (Mean Score)	Range of Motion - Flexion (Degrees)	Range of Motion - Abduction (Degrees)
3 Weeks Post-op	6	100°	90°
3 Months Post-op	4	120°	110°
6 Months Post-op	2	140°	130°

Discussion

The functional integrity of the spinal accessory nerve (SAN) following various neck dissection techniques offers a significant insight into the postoperative outcomes for patients with head and neck cancer. This study elucidates the subtle yet

profound impacts that different surgical approaches can have on SAN functionality and consequently on shoulder mobility and overall quality of life. [9] Elective neck dissection, while crucial for managing lymph node metastases, distinctly affects SAN function more than observational approaches. Initial reductions in SAN functionality, as seen in

the immediate postoperative assessments, highlight the physical trauma induced by radical dissections.

However, the gradual recuperation of nerve function over six months suggests that with careful surgical technique and effective postoperative rehabilitation, long-term deficits can be minimized. [10,11] The varying incidence of shoulder dysfunction across dissection types underscores the need for tailored surgical strategies. Radical neck dissection poses a higher risk of moderate shoulder dysfunction compared to modified and selective techniques, which mostly resulted in mild symptoms. These findings suggest that less extensive dissections, when oncologically permissible, may be advantageous in preserving motor function and reducing postoperative morbidity. [12,13]

EMG assessments provide a quantifiable measure of muscle and nerve impairment and recovery. The observed improvements in EMG amplitudes for the trapezius muscle across all sections from three to six months postoperatively are indicative of nerve regeneration or successful adaptation through compensatory mechanisms. [14]

The role of physiotherapy emerged as a cornerstone in enhancing recovery. Significant improvements in pain management and shoulder mobility following structured physiotherapy regimens point to the necessity of integrating these interventions early and maintaining them throughout the recovery period to optimize outcomes.

Conclusion

The study conclusively demonstrates that while neck dissection is indispensable for controlling head and neck cancer, it necessitates a balanced approach to minimize functional loss. The type of neck dissection performed significantly influences the extent of SAN injury and subsequent shoulder dysfunction. Proactive measures, including meticulous surgical techniques to preserve nerve integrity and comprehensive postoperative rehabilitation, are critical in mitigating these effects. Ultimately, the goal is to not only extend survival but also preserve the quality of life, underscoring the need for ongoing refinement of both surgical and rehabilitative practices.

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